

JURISPRUDENCE

CHILD SUBSTITUTION AS A CRIME THAT INFRINGES ON A CHILD'S RIGHT TO LIVE AND BE RAISED IN A FAMILY

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Abstract

The article considers a child's guaranteed right to live and grow up in a family as his basic right, which is greatly damaged by the implementation of the crime, stipulated by article 136 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Kazakhstan. The social danger of the crime in question lies in the fact that as a result of its commission the blood ties of kinship are forcibly severed, and the natural relations between parents and children are disturbed.

A person's origins are falsified, distorted. The mental health and, consequently, the child's normal development, as well as the child's right to live and be brought up in a family, are particularly at risk when the substitution is detected. The article notes that the approach to the child, enshrined in chapter 10 of the Code on Marriage (Matrimony and Family), is consistent with the obligations undertaken by Kazakhstan to fully protect the rights and interests of the child. Chief among these is a child's right to live and be brought up in a family (whether natural or foster).

Keywords: child's right, family, crime, substitution, living and growing up in a family

The right of the child to live and grow up in a family plays an overriding systemic role in the modus operandi of minors. The axiom is that the best personal environment for the child's development is the family. Different views have been expressed in the literature regarding the content of the child's right to live and be brought up in the family. A group of authors is of the view that this right is complex and generalisable. In their opinion, the right of the child to know his/her parents, to live together with them, to receive care from them, to respect their dignity are the structural elements of the right to live and be brought up in a family [1, p.156].

From the wording of the child's right to live and be brought up in a family, the term 'in a family' must be interpreted broadly. The lawmaker is undoubtedly referring primarily to the blood family.

When a child loses parental care, this right is ensured through a surrogate family: adoptive parents, guardians, tutors and foster families. This conclusion follows from the analysis of the Marriage (Matrimony) and Family Code [2]. The specific nature of the subject of the right to live and be brought up in a family consists of his physical helplessness and inability to understand the significance of the circumstances around him in his early childhood, determines also the ratio of powers in the said right.

The right of the child to live and grow up in a family belongs to the family's individual non-property rights and is inextricably linked to other individual non-property and property rights established in other branches of law.

A special chapter in the Criminal Code is devoted to criminal offences against the family and minors. Two of these are substitution (Article 136) and trafficking in minors (Article 135) which directly infringe a minor's right to live with his or her parents and be brought up in a family.

The object of the above criminal offences is the social relations arising out of the exercise of the child's right to live and be brought up in a family. They harm the rights provided for in the Convention on the Rights of the Child: the right of the child to know his or her parents and to be cared for by them (Article 7); the right not to be separated from his or her parents and to maintain regular contact with them (Article 9) [3].

These provisions lead to the conclusion that when a child is replaced, his or her right to know and be cared for by his or her parents and his or her right to maintain his or her identity is violated.

In this case, the substitution of a child encroaches on the family right of the child to live and be brought up in his or her own family.

O. Kolmakova considers it inappropriate to limit the object of the considered crime only to the personality of a minor, as child substitution also violates the rights of parents to live with their child and bring him up [4, p.83].

Of course, the interests of the parents or the family as a whole are also affected when this crime is committed. And this is probably the only crime where it is very difficult to establish an equal balance of its objects.

It should be noted, however, that in most cases newborns are replaced in maternity homes, hospitals, childcare facilities, perinatal centers, prams near home, spa facilities, and other medical facilities, before the mother or other relatives have had a chance to identify the child's unique identifying characteristics.

The objective necessity of socialization of minors and their dependence on adults are those features of society which determine its vital activity. For quite a long period of time children were seen as an object of parental authority, and only at the end of the 19th century, under the influence of a number of negative phenomena, the world community realized the need to secure such rights for minors, which would ensure their well-being, development and survival. Child protection laws

first emerged in individual countries, and over time international legal instruments on the rights of minors were adopted as well. There has thus been a formal recognition of minors as persons with an autonomous legal status. However, no clear guarantees have been elaborated to facilitate the protection and realization of minors' rights.

The subject of child substitution, according to V. V. Timoshchenko can be parents, medical personnel of maternity hospitals and children's institutions, as well as other interested persons [5, p.23]. However, in reality this crime can be committed by employees of medical institution or with their complicity or negligence. The 1989 UN Convention on the Rights of the Child not only proclaimed the rights of the child, including the right to life and upbringing in a family, but also created a system of guarantees. Since then, issues concerning the protection of various, especially family rights of children, have begun to be introduced into the legislative process. In 2012, the Marriage (Marriage and Family) Code was enacted. Chapter 11 enshrines a whole system of rights for minors. In the first place is the minor's right to live and be brought up in a family. Accordingly, the family upbringing provides an opportunity to make a special approach to each child, taking into account his or her personal, physical and other characteristics [6, p.109]. The quality of the upbringing of a person under the age of majority - as O.S. Kolmakova argues - depends on ensuring a number of their basic rights in the society and the state [4, p.21].

A child's personal rights are recognised as his or her right to life and to know and be cared for by his or her mother, father, siblings and others, to live and communicate with them, to have dignity and honour, to be brought up by close relatives, etc.

This right is also guaranteed by the Law of RK "On the Rights of the Child in the Republic of Kazakhstan". [7]. A system of guarantees for the implementation and protection of this right is still being developed at the international and domestic level in rule-making and law-enforcement activities. In doctrine there is also a process of quantitative accumulation of necessary information. Therefore, each work devoted to this problem is a certain contribution to science. Under the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child, minors are defined as persons under 18 years of age. All rights under the Convention and national law, including the right to live and be brought up in a family, continue until that age. A child's right to live and grow up in a family springs from the fact of birth, irrespective of the determination of his or her origin, and ends only at his or her death or majority. No other circumstances, including acquisition of full civil capacity, entail loss of that right before reaching the age of majority. Consequently, minors who have left the family are entitled to return to it at any time. The acquisition by marriage or emancipation of full civil capacity by a minor should not impair the scope of family rights, in particular the right to live and be brought up in the family and the right to maintenance. The fundamental and best prerequisite for the realization of the right of the child to live and grow up in a family is the nuclear family, and for

this reason family protection legislation should contain a special provision stipulating that placement in another family for permanent upbringing is an exceptional measure which is applied only when the child cannot live in the nuclear family. A child's right to live and be brought up in a family is of a complex legal nature and, as an element of family legal capacity, it is realized in general regulatory legal relations. As a subjective right belonging to an individual, it is exercised in family, civil, housing and other legal relations. Newly adopted laws affecting a child's right to live and be brought up in a family must be harmonized with each other and with existing laws in order to avoid blocking a minor's right to live and be brought up in a family.

It is noted that the right of minors to live and be brought up in a family is a family law, although the mechanism for its implementation and protection is also enshrined in the rules of other branches of law, and therefore it is important that the rules of the various legal branches containing this mechanism are mutually consistent, not blocking but facilitating its implementation. In this case, the word "family" should be understood broadly, referring not only to the kinship family, but also to a substitute family if the minor is displaced from his or her birth family or if it, for various reasons, no longer exists. The minor's right to live and grow up in a family is a personal inalienable right, arising from the very fact of birth and terminating either by death or by reaching the age of majority. In the dissertator's view, no other circumstances can serve as grounds for the termination of this right, including the acquisition by a minor of full civil capacity due to marriage or emancipation. As long as a person has not reached the age of majority, he or she has the right to return to the family at any time and continue to live there. At the same time, the content of the right to live and be brought up in a family as a measure of a minor's possible behaviour is rather limited. Because of his social status, his lack of independent sources of subsistence, his economic and psychological dependence on adults, etc. - he cannot renounce this right, i.e. to live outside the family, even if this contradicts not only his wishes but also his legitimate interests. Based on public law principles, we can say that a minor is not only entitled but in the absolute majority of cases obliged to live and be brought up in a family, except in cases where the minor, having been left without parental care, prefers placement in an institution rather than in a substitute family. Living in a natural family is the basic and best condition for realising a child's right to live and grow up in a family. Living and bringing up a minor in a particular family generates, at the very least, the right to use the living space, which may limit the rights and interests of others. In this sense, the mechanism for realising this right of a minor is ineffective.

Among family legal relations, there are those in which the rights of minors do not correspond to the corresponding responsibilities of adults, hence there is no mechanism for implementing and protecting these rights. For example, a minor's right to live and be brought up in a family is closely linked to his or her right to communicate with grandparents, brothers,

sisters and other blood relatives, while the latter have no obligation to communicate with the minor and cannot be forced to do so against their wishes. The law only imposes a duty on parents not to hinder their child's communication with his or her blood relatives. The same obligation is imposed on substitute parents, but this does not apply to adoptive parents. Even if the adoptive parent objects, the court cannot order the adoptive parent to allow the adoptive parent to allow the blood relatives access to the adopted minor.

The right of minors to live and be brought up in a family is the most difficult to implement in the norms of family law. It is realised through a system of other personal non-property rights: the right to respect for a minor's human dignity, the right to protection of his/her honour and dignity, which, in the author's opinion, requires special enshrinement as the duty of legal representatives to protect a minor's honour and dignity, the right to family education, the right to know his/her parents and other blood relatives as far as possible, etc. Sometimes, this right is realised through the respective responsibilities of parents and surrogate parents. For example, these persons are obliged to take care of the health of minors, to ensure that they receive a basic (general) education, etc.

The realization of a minor's right to live and be brought up in a family passes through a number of stages: the child is taken from the maternity home, placed in the family, his or her birth is registered, his or her name is given and he or she is identified within and outside the family, nationality is determined, feeding and care are provided for, etc. As the child develops, the activities of the parents or other caregivers become more intense, and then the activities of the juvenile as a family member are added to these activities. Thus, in the normal course of all stages of the implementation of this right of the minor, the protection mechanism is not triggered - it is not necessary. Such a need is precisely caused by the impossibility of realising the right due to its infringement. For this reason, enforcement and protection do not occur simultaneously. To a certain extent, their relationship can be seen as a unity of opposites. On the question of whether the right to protection is a third element of a subjective right or an autonomous right, the author takes the position that the right to protection is autonomous, as he believes that this legal construction can protect not only the rights but also the legitimate interests of the child, including his right to live and be brought up in a family.

As we have already said, children must live and be brought up in a family, this right being granted by the territorial unit of the authorised state body for child protection: in the absence of parents, deprivation of parental rights or in other cases of loss of parental care [8, p. 124].

The best interest of the child is a set of fundamental principles of the convention aimed at protecting the rights of the child and providing the necessary conditions to fully meet his needs for physical and psychological development, as well as limiting unlimited power over adults (for example, guardians, teachers, guardianship authorities, law enforcement agencies, parents, doctors, etc.).

Every child has the right to live with his or her birth parents. No one has the right to deprive him or her of that right. By substituting a newborn child, the offender deprives the child of his family, violates his right to live with his parents, to receive their upbringing, to know his parents, etc.

A child's right to live and be brought up in a family can also be realised by other means: adoption as one of the best ways to place children; placement with a guardian or custodian; and placement in a foster family, which differs from the adopted family in that it is a temporary contractual relationship. However, these temporary substitute family arrangements will not replace the child's biological parents. For this reason, the country's family and criminal law makes it possible to seek protection of the rights of underage children from the competent State authorities. The protection of the family should be pursued from the perspective of the long-term development interests of society through the development and implementation of a State Family Policy Strategy.

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